
Assessing the Impact of Political Interference on the Operational Efficiency of Trade Unions in Tanzania: A case Study of the Tanzania Teachers' Union (TTU)

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the impact of political interference on the operational efficiency of trade unions in Tanzania, focusing on the Tanzania Teachers' Union (TTU) as a case study. Using a qualitative research design, data were collected from TTU members, union leaders, and government officials to explore how external political forces influence TTU's leadership, internal governance, and service delivery. Thematic analysis revealed that political actors interfere in leadership appointments, influence decision-making processes, and shape service implementation, thereby compromising the union's autonomy and effectiveness. Political loyalty among leaders was seen to undermine trust, reduce member engagement, and shift the union's focus from advocacy to appeasement. These findings suggest that for TTU to fulfil its mission, it must restore democratic processes, enhance transparency, and safeguard its independence from political interests. The study contributes to ongoing debates on trade union autonomy in politically sensitive environments and provides practical recommendations for strengthening union governance in Tanzania.

Keywords: *Political interference, trade unions, leadership, governance, Tanzania, service delivery.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Trade unions are critical institutions for representing workers' interests, advocating for improved working conditions, and contributing to fair labor practices. Globally, their emergence was driven by the collective need to counter exploitation, especially during the industrial revolution when factory workers began organizing to secure better wages and safer workplaces (Visser, 2019). Over the decades, trade unions have evolved into key stakeholders in national policy processes, influencing labor laws, public service reforms, and collective bargaining frameworks (Reddy, 2022). However, despite their importance, trade unions increasingly face challenges that threaten their autonomy and operational efficiency one of the most pressing being political interference.

Political interference in trade union operations is a global concern. According to the International Labor Organization (ILO), political interference occurs when governments, political parties, or state actors manipulate or exert undue influence over union decisions, leadership appointments, and collective actions (Koliev, 2022). Such interference undermines union autonomy, weakens leadership independence, and distorts union priorities away from workers' needs. In the United States, unions like the United Auto Workers have experienced political and corporate pressure affecting their leadership elections and negotiation strategies (Oghlanian et al., 2023). Similarly, in India, unions affiliated with ruling parties often compromise their bargaining power by placing political loyalty above workers' welfare (Miyamura, 2018). These patterns indicate a broader global trend where trade unions are vulnerable to being politicized and repurposed for political agendas rather than worker advocacy.

In the African context, political interference has been particularly evident in countries where trade unions historically served both labour and political functions. For example, the Congress of South African Trade Unions (COSATU) has had strong links with the African National Congress (ANC), a relationship that has brought both influence and constraints. Zulu (2021) and Reddy (2024) observe that while this political alliance initially strengthened labour rights advocacy, it eventually led to conflicts of interest that compromised COSATU's autonomy. Similarly, in Kenya, Kuja (2022) found that political actors often influence leadership appointments in the Kenya National Union of Teachers (KNUT), which has negatively affected the union's ability to independently represent teachers' interests. These examples show that when unions are politically co-opted, their leadership and decision-making structures are often redirected to serve political ends rather than the needs of their members.

In Tanzania, the problem of political interference in trade unions can be traced back to the single-party era under Chama Cha Mapinduzi (CCM). During this time, unions were tightly controlled by the state, and even after the transition to multi-party politics, their independence has remained constrained. The legal framework governing trade unions—particularly the Public Service Act (2003), the Employment and Labour Relations Act (2004), and the Public Service Negotiating Machinery imposes limitations on collective bargaining and places unions under strong government oversight. For instance, the Public Service Negotiating Machinery requires that all negotiations by public sector unions be cleared through centralized government bodies, which significantly restricts the unions' autonomy to act on behalf of their members (Elias et al., 2022). The Tanzania Teachers' Union (TTU) offers a compelling case study of how political interference affects trade union operations. Established to protect teachers' rights, promote professional development, and advocate for

better working conditions, TTU has played an important role in Tanzania's education system. Its mission emphasizes promoting the dignity of the teaching profession, while its vision seeks to ensure quality education for all Tanzanians (TTU, 2024). However, political interference has increasingly undermined the union's ability to fulfill this mission. Research by Mndeme (2023) and Elias and Iramba (2022) shows that political actors often influence TTU's leadership elections and strategic decisions, causing leaders to align with government agendas rather than member interests. As a result, collective bargaining has weakened, internal communication is limited, and members are increasingly disengaged from union activities.

In addition to political pressures, TTU faces operational challenges such as weak transparency, limited member participation, and fragmented representation due to the presence of multiple competing unions (Ally & John, 2021). These internal inefficiencies further compromise TTU's effectiveness. However, the most persistent issue remains the union's limited autonomy due to political interference embedded in both formal structures and informal political expectations. Legislative instruments like the Public Service Act and the control exerted through the Ministry of Education and Vocational Training continue to restrict the union's ability to advocate independently, negotiate on behalf of its members, or hold leadership accountable to its base.

Despite these challenges, there is limited empirical research in Tanzania that examines the direct impact of political interference on trade union operations particularly in terms of internal governance, decision-making processes, and service delivery outcomes. Most existing studies, such as those by Traianou (2023) and Aslam et al. (2019), focus on union strategies or general political relationships but do not investigate how political interference specifically affects a union's efficiency from within. The case of TTU, with its national importance and wide membership base, provides an important opportunity to study how political factors constrain the daily and strategic functioning of a major public-sector union. However, this study seeks to address this gap by assessing the impact of political interference on the operational efficiency of trade unions in Tanzania, with TTU as a case study. It will explore not only how political actors influence leadership and decision-making but also how legal frameworks and broader political structures enable or perpetuate such interference. By understanding these dynamics, the study aims to offer practical recommendations to strengthen union autonomy, promote internal accountability, and reform legal structures that currently undermine trade union independence. In doing so, it contributes both to academic understanding and to ongoing policy debates about labour rights and democratic governance in Tanzania.

1.1 Statement of the Research Problem

Trade unions, including the Tanzania Teachers' Union (TTU), play a vital role in promoting the welfare of teachers and protecting their labour rights. However, political interference remains a growing concern, especially in Tanzania's public sector unions. TTU, in particular, has experienced cases where political actors influence leadership appointments, union elections, and strategic decisions. For example, Elias and Iramba (2022) report that TTU leaders often align with ruling party interests, which undermines their ability to advocate independently for teachers. Similarly, Mndeme (2023) shows that government-affiliated leaders are frequently installed in TTU's top positions, resulting in reduced transparency, weakened collective bargaining, and declining membership participation.

This political interference directly affects the operational efficiency of TTU. Studies reveal that politically influenced leaders prioritize political agendas over member welfare, leading to delayed decision-making, internal conflicts, and ineffective service delivery (Aslam et al. 2019; Wehner & Thies, 2021). Orelowitz (2021) and Koliev (2022) further argue that such interference erodes trust in union governance, limits autonomy, and reduces union performance. When union leadership is compromised, teachers' grievances go unaddressed, morale declines, and the quality of education suffers. If these conditions persist, TTU risks losing credibility, weakening its influence in education policymaking and failing its mandate.

Despite these concerns, limited research has focused on how political interference affects the internal functioning of TTU especially in terms of governance, leadership, and decision-making processes. This study seeks to fill that gap by assessing the impact of political interference on TTU's operational efficiency and by identifying legal and institutional reforms to enhance union independence and performance.

1.2 Research Questions

- i. What are the forms and sources of political interference affecting the operations of the Tanzania Teachers' Union (TTU)?
- ii. How does political interference impact the internal governance, leadership, and decision-making of TTU?
- iii. In what ways does political interference affect TTU's ability to deliver services and achieve its mission and vision?

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical Review

2.1.1 Resource Dependence Theory (RDT)

The Resource Dependence Theory (RDT), developed by Pfeffer and Salancik in 1978, argues that organizations are significantly influenced by external forces, especially when they rely on external resources for their operations and survival. The theory states that organizations often adapt their behavior, strategies, and decisions in response to external forces, such as political actors, that control or influence the flow of critical resources like funding, recognition, or logistical support. These external influences can constrain an organization's autonomy and efficiency, ultimately shaping its ability to achieve its goals.

The first objective, examining the effects of political interference on TTU's mission and vision, relates to how resource control by political actors can reshape the organization's goals. The second objective, assessing political influence on TTU's leadership, reflects how external forces can determine leadership selection and decision-making within the union. The third objective, evaluating the impact of political interference on TTU's decision-making process, links to how external resource control affects the union's autonomy in making strategic decisions.

RDT was valuable in this study due to its strong explanatory power regarding how external forces, particularly political actors, influence organizational behavior. It provides clear insights into the mechanisms by which resource dependency constrains autonomy and efficiency, helping to explain the challenges faced by TTU in navigating political

interference. Additionally, RDT offers practical guidance on how organizations like TTU can reduce vulnerability to external pressures, making it a versatile framework for understanding trade union dynamics in politically sensitive contexts.

A notable limitation of RDT is its focus on external factors, often neglecting internal organizational elements such as leadership, culture, and resilience. Another critique of RDT is its limited attention to how organizations can proactively transform their strategies to reduce dependence on external resources. To address this limitation, the study incorporates Transformational Leadership Theory as a complementary framework. Transformational Leadership Theory emphasizes the role of strong, visionary leadership in navigating external challenges and maintaining organizational focus and efficiency despite external pressures. This allows for a more holistic understanding of how TTU can counteract political interference by strengthening its internal capacity.

2.1.2 Transformational Leadership Theory (TLT)

Transformational Leadership Theory (TLT) was introduced by James MacGregor Burns in 1978 and later expanded by Bernard Bass in 1985. The theory explains how leaders can inspire, motivate, and transform their followers to achieve organizational goals by fostering trust, encouraging innovation, and aligning individual goals with collective objectives. In the context of this study, Transformational Leadership Theory highlights the importance of visionary and effective leadership within the Tanzania Teachers Union (TTU) to counteract political interference. The theory suggests that transformational leaders can inspire their teams to overcome external challenges, such as political influence, and focus on achieving the union's mission and vision. By building trust and commitment among members, these leaders can maintain the union's integrity and effectiveness, even under political pressure. This study uses key variables from Transformational Leadership Theory, including inspirational motivation, individualized consideration, and intellectual stimulation.

This theory focused on leadership's role in driving change and overcoming challenges. It emphasizes leaders' ability to motivate and unite members, crucial for TTU amidst political interference. A transformational leader could inspire TTU members to pursue shared goals, like advocating for teachers' rights, while resisting external influences. The theory also provides insights on strengthening TTU leadership and autonomy. Another critique is that, transformational leadership might not always be feasible in organizations with rigid structures or limited resources. In such cases, leaders may struggle to inspire or implement innovative strategies. This limitation is addressed in the study by exploring how TTU leaders can balance visionary leadership with pragmatic approaches to counteract political interference, such as fostering member unity and leveraging internal resources effectively. The combination of these two theories offered a comprehensive framework for analyzing TTU's challenges and identifying strategies to enhance its effectiveness despite political pressures.

2.2 Empirical Literature Review

2.2.1 Effects of Political Interference on Trade Union's Mission and Vision

Political interference in trade unions significantly influences their mission and long-term goals, often shifting focus from member welfare to political loyalty. For instance, Aslam et al. (2019) found that in India, the Indian National Trade Union Congress (INTUC) affiliated with the ruling party had gradually shifted its focus from advocating for teachers' rights to serving broader political interests. As a result, the union's mission of protecting

educational standards and teachers' working conditions was diluted in favors of electoral and party objectives. The study reveals that such unions, initially formed for professional or labour-related goals, increasingly become tools of incumbent political agendas, compromising their independence and long-term vision.

In Kenya, the Kenya National Union of Teachers (KNUT) has faced substantial political interference. Kuja (2022) reports that government actors have manipulated leadership elections within KNUT to install politically loyal leaders. This manipulation led to internal divisions, weakening the union's cohesion and shifting its mission away from educational reform and toward political survival. Consequently, KNUT's ability to effectively represent its members and contribute to national education policy became secondary to appeasing political stakeholders. In South Africa, Zulu (2021) examined the Congress of South African Trade Unions (COSATU) and noted that although the union was actively involved in climate justice advocacy, its foundational mission of protecting workers' rights was weakened due to close ties with the African National Congress (ANC). Political interference manifested through policy alignment, where union leaders were pressured to support party positions even when they conflicted with workers' interests. This alliance blurred the union's original vision, diverting attention from core labour priorities to political agendas, including electoral strategies and governance partnerships.

Turning to Tanzania, Ng'eleshi et al. (2022) discuss the influence of political interference on the Tanzania Teachers' Union (TTU). They note that while collective bargaining has improved teachers' welfare in some cases, political interference distorts the negotiation process. Politically aligned leaders are often appointed or supported by the ruling party, which results in weakened union bargaining power. Instead of prioritizing the union's mission to advocate for quality education and fair working conditions, leaders are compelled to align with government policy positions. Similarly, Elias and Iramba (2022) observe that the existence of multiple politically influenced unions in Tanzania has led to competition and internal conflict. These factions, often aligned with different political parties, undermine TTU's ability to provide unified professional development and advocacy, thereby weakening its core educational mission. While these studies highlight critical challenges, few explore the long-term consequences of political interference on unions' strategic direction. Zulu (2021) rightly notes that political interference contributes to union fragmentation in South Africa, yet its broader impact on altering union missions remains underexplored. Fragmentation and politicization suggest more than disunity they point to a redirection of union goals toward serving external political interests. However, studies such as Aslam et al. (2019) and Kuja (2022) tend to focus on short-term outcomes, such as weakened bargaining power or compromised leadership, rather than the strategic, mission-level impact over time.

Therefore, while there is growing literature on political interference in trade unions, there remains a critical gap in understanding how such interference affects the long-term vision and purpose of unions, particularly in the context of Tanzania. This study aims to fill that gap by investigating how political influence alters TTU's ability to pursue its mission of protecting teachers' welfare and promoting quality education. By exploring these dynamics over time, the research will contribute to a deeper understanding of how political factors compromise union efficiency at a structural level.

2.2.2 Influence of Political Interference on Trade Union's Leadership

Political interference in trade unions globally has serious consequences on leadership. Traianou (2023) discusses how political intervention affects union leadership, particularly

during education reforms. The research shows that political players often influence union officials who align with their ideologies, rather than those best suited to promote workers' interests. This leads to union leadership often being composed of individuals with limited ability to represent the union and its members effectively. Such interference can compromise the union's credibility, reducing officials' ability to advocate for teachers' agendas and education reforms.

In Africa, Moswela and Kgosidialwa (2019) describe the challenges to leadership in schools. This study reveals how political interferences make it difficult for school leaders to perform their functions well, as most political appointees lack professional competence in education but are instead rewarded for political loyalty. This makes it difficult for school leaders to effect change in education or fight for teacher's freedom, which mirrors the life of trade union leaders. Furthermore, Mbandlwa et al. (2020) agree that political interference is central to undermining leadership. They explain that political pressure on local leaders leads to leaders who care more about their political benefactors than the people or organizations they are supposed to represent.

Mndeme (2023) examines how political influence weakens the Tanzania Teachers Union (TTU) by appointing leaders with political ties instead of teacher advocates, undermining union autonomy. University political leadership pressures TTU into decisions against members' interests. Elias and Iramba (2022) highlight that political intervention centralizes union leadership, shifting focus from professional learning to political agendas, causing division and reducing support for teacher development. Ally and John (2021) suggest that political affiliations weaken grievance handling, as leaders prioritize politics over teachers' concerns. It was also discussed about political intervention in grievance processing but overlook its impact on union leadership, strategy, and efficiency. This study will expand on their work by examining its relevance to TTU leadership in Tanzania. Studies like Mndeme (2023), Traianou (2023), and Mbandlwa et al. (2020) do not directly address how political interference affects TTU's strategic decisions. This study will fill these gaps by assessing political interference's influence on TTU leadership.

2.2.3 Effects of Political Interference on Trade Union's Decision-Making Process

Globally, Traianou (2023) also shows that political actors interfere with union decisions depending on governmental education policies, which hinders union leaders from making decisions for their members. Teachers' welfare and professional development were negotiated and influenced by political interferences, which compromise the final decisions. Also, it argued about influence of political actors on decisions, the emphasis is made on education instead of on those tendencies in general and their influence on decision-making in the scope of unionization, particularly teachers' unions. Koliev (2022), reveals the role of political interference in shaping national labor regulations and, by extension, the decision-making processes of trade unions. The study also points out that the ILO has attempted to reduce political interference in labour decisions, but national political processes in many countries give precedence to national political processes a result, the decision making by unions is influenced. From Koliev (2022), there is useful information concerning how political influence affects union decisions; however, the emphasis is given to the national labour laws rather than the decision making within unions such as the TTU.

In Africa, Odhiambo (2019), looks at the political aspects that underpin decision making among teachers' unions in East Africa. This research established that political concerns often compel authorities to make choices that favor the government instead of the

teachers especially where unions are hijacked by political factions. This leads to the fact that teachers' benefits and welfare are not promoted by the leadership of the union because the union leaders may not want to make tough decisions that may offend the political leaders. Haile and Smit (2021) explain the extent of political interferences in the educational sector, including how it influences school leaders' decisions. Although their main concern is not trading unions but school governance, they demonstrate that political involvement hampers leaders' decision-making discretion, a factor that impacts on the quality of education as well as the growth of teachers' profession. Furthermore, Kuja (2022) study examines the nature and extent of the relationship between political factors and trade union strategies and how these strategies affect decision-making within unions. This paper reveals that political intervention results in decisions that are not in the best interest of teachers since union officials attempt to navigate the politicization process in the best interest of all union members.

Tanzania has experienced political interference in the Tanzania Teachers Union (TTU). Mndeme (2023) notes that such interference limits TTU's autonomy, especially in advocating for teachers' rights. Government influence often prioritizes policies over teachers' interests, undermining the union's role. The study also highlights how government interference affects TTU's decision-making. Similarly, Mtisho and Rutenge (2024) show that political influence drives decisions favoring the political system. This study will address these gaps by evaluating political interference's impact on TTU's decision-making process.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Approach

This study adopted a qualitative research approach because the aim was to explore how political interference influenced the operational efficiency of the Tanzania Teachers' Union (TTU). Political interference involves complex relationships, hidden power structures, and subjective experiences that cannot be captured through numerical data. Qualitative research allows for in-depth investigation of such dynamics through open-ended, flexible methods. It was particularly suitable for understanding perceptions, motivations, and the lived realities of those affected.

3.2 Research Design

This study adopted a case study design to investigate the effects of political interference on TTU's mission, leadership, and decision-making processes. A case study design entails an in-depth study of a specific person, group, organization, or event in its natural setting (Yin, 2018). In this research, the TTU served as the "case." This design was particularly appropriate since the research focused on a specific organization (TTU) and a specific phenomenon (political interference) within that organization's unique context.

3.3 Study Area

This study was conducted in Tanzania, focusing on the Tanzania Teachers' Union (TTU). Tanzania provided an ideal context for the research due to its well-documented history of trade unionism and the reported cases of political interference in trade union affairs (Mndeme, 2023). The selection of Tanzania was scientifically justified based on the forefront of TTU in advocating for teachers' rights, yet concerns have been raised about government influence in its operations, making it a relevant case for analysis (Kuja, 2022). Also,

Tanzania's legal and institutional framework governing trade unions and labour relations offered a structured environment to evaluate the dynamics of political interference, as highlighted in previous studies on labour regulation (Koliev, 2022).

3.4 Population of the Study

This study carried out heterogeneous population in multiple categories of stakeholders with diverse experiences, interests, and roles within TTU and its engagement with political actors. The study focused on three main groups which were Teachers (TTU Members), TTU Leaders, and Government Officials. Each of these groups was differently affected by political interference. Teachers, as TTU members, constituted the largest category in the population. The TTU records indicated a total membership of 247,860 teachers (ttu.or.tz, 2025). Given that these teachers were directly impacted by the union's operations. They provided essential insights into how political interference influenced TTU's mission, vision, and operational efficiency. TTU leaders both at national and regional levels played crucial roles in managing the union and steering its decision-making processes. While the TTU website documented only three National TTU Leaders, the total number of Regional Leaders was not officially recorded. The government officials, particularly those from the Ministry of Education and the Department of Labour and Employment, were also part of the population.

3.5 Sample Size and Sampling Procedure

3.5.1 Sample Size

This study adopted a sample size of 40 participants. Following Braun and Clarke's (2021) suggestion that meaning saturation in qualitative studies typically occurs within 20 to 40 interviews. Given the heterogeneous nature of the study population, the study assumes to employ 20 teachers, 10 TTU leaders, and 10 government officials through which the sample size balanced and inclusive representation of the key stakeholders affected by political interference in TTU's operations. Following that, the sample distribution is structured to reflect the relative influence.

3.5.2 Sampling Procedure

A purposive and Snowball sampling techniques were employed to select participants for this study. In applying non-probability sampling techniques, the participants were selected basing on their knowledge, experience, or role within the organization which was relevant to the research question (Palinkas et al., 2015). This strategy was appropriate for this study as it sought to gather insights from individuals who were most likely to have valuable information about the impact of political interference on the TTU.

Snowball sampling involves asking the initial participants to refer other people who meet the study's inclusion criteria (Biernacki & Waldorf, 1981). This method was particularly helpful for reaching individuals who were otherwise difficult to access through conventional sampling methods.

3.6 Data Collection Methods

The study employed semi-structured interviews and document review methods of data collection. It enabled the collection of rich, qualitative data on the complex dynamics of political interference within the TTU (Melissa & Lisa, 2019). An interview guide was

developed to frame the discussions, containing key themes and open-ended questions aligned with the study's research objectives. The guide included topics such as the impact of political interference on TTU's mission and vision, its influence on leadership, effects on decision-making, personal experiences, and coping mechanisms. The interviews were also audio-recorded (with permission) to ensure accurate transcription for analysis. The semi-structured format also allowed participants to express their perspectives in their own terms and fostering more genuine responses.

3.7 Data Analysis

Data were analyzed using thematic analysis. Salmona and Kaczynski (2024) outlined thematic analysis enables researchers to move beyond simple descriptions of data to interpret meanings and draw deeper conclusions. The process began with familiarization with the data, followed by verbatim transcription of all interview recordings. Both inductive and deductive coding methods were employed. Deductive coding was informed by the study's research questions. While inductive coding allowed the identification of unexpected themes emerging from the data. The coding process involved identifying and categorizing significant segments of text that related to patterns of political interference, leadership challenges, and union operations. Emerging themes were then defined and supported with direct excerpts from participant transcripts.

3.8 Validity and Reliability of the Study

3.8.1 Validity

To ensure credibility, the study engaged in prolonged interaction with participants and conducted triangulation of data sources by collecting perspectives from teachers, TTU leaders, and government officials. Member checking was employed by sharing emerging findings with selected participants to confirm accuracy and interpretation. Rich contextual descriptions were provided to support transferability, allowing others to assess the applicability of the findings to different contexts. An audit trail documenting key decisions, processes, and analytical steps was maintained throughout the study to support dependability. To demonstrate confirmability, the study incorporated direct quotations from participants to ground interpretations in the data, ensuring that findings were shaped by respondents' experiences rather than researcher bias.

3.8.2 Reliability

To ensure reliability, a semi-structured interview guide was developed and used consistently across all interviews. Interviewers were trained to follow the guide while also allowing flexibility for probing, ensuring comparable data collection across different participants. All interviews were audio-recorded, transcribed verbatim, and systematically documented to maintain procedural consistency. By documenting and following a transparent analysis framework, the study enhanced the consistency and repeatability of the analytical process.

3.9 Ethical Consideration

Ethical principles were prioritized throughout the data generation and analysis process. Participants were fully informed about the purpose of the research, their right to confidentiality, and their freedom to withdraw at any point without consequence. Prior to the

interviews, written informed consent was obtained from all participants. All interviews were conducted with respect for participants' autonomy and dignity. To protect participant identities, all personal identifiers were removed during transcription, and data were anonymized. Interview recordings, transcripts, and analysis notes were securely stored in password-protected files accessible only to the research team. Ethical clearance was also obtained from relevant institutional bodies prior to data collection.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Forms and Sources of Political Interference Affecting TTU

The study revealed three major manifestations of political interference: manipulation of leadership selection processes, involvement of government actors in internal union operations, and deliberate fragmentation of the union's unity through political manoeuvres.

4.1.1 Manipulation of leadership selection processes

Several TTU members expressed concerns about political influence in the selection of union leaders. According to many respondents, political affiliation often takes precedence over professional merit, thereby compromising the democratic ideals of the union. One teacher from Mwanza shared,

"Sometimes it seems like those who are close to political leaders are the ones who get selected to lead, even if they haven't really been active in union matters" (Teacher 4).

Another teacher reinforced this perception, noting,

"During elections, you get the feeling that some candidates already have outside support, and the union members' opinions don't matter much" (Teacher 9).

A TTU leader also lamented,

"There are moments when you see someone getting a leadership position and wonder whether it was about qualifications or political alignment" (Leader 3).

These findings suggest that political loyalty has, in some instances, superseded union loyalty, thereby reducing the union's internal accountability and undermining members' confidence in their leaders.

4.1.2 Involvement of government actors in internal union operations

In addition to leadership interference, many respondents highlighted how TTU's internal operations are often influenced by government actors. Rather than being consulted as an independent stakeholder, the union is frequently expected to endorse predetermined decisions made by political authorities. A TTU leader commented,

"In some meetings with government officials, the conversation is more about informing us what has been decided, not really asking for our input" (Leader 2).

A teacher from Dar es Salaam further elaborated,

“When TTU tries to organize something for teachers, there’s always a call or visit from someone in the district telling them to stop or adjust the plan” (Teacher 3).

Another respondent noted,

“We are sometimes told to go along with what is already agreed, even when it doesn’t benefit teachers directly” (Teacher 7).

These accounts portray a constrained operational space, where TTU’s autonomy is undermined by constant external monitoring and interference.

4.1.3 Deliberate fragmentation of the union’s unity through political man oeuvres

Government officials who participated in the study also confirmed a more subtle form of interference fragmentation of TTU’s influence through the promotion of alternative unions. Respondents admitted that political actors sometimes support or encourage the proliferation of smaller unions to dilute TTU’s bargaining power. One government official stated,

“There are several teacher unions now, and not all of them agree with TTU that can be helpful for balance” (Gov’t Official 5).

Another observed,

“Having many unions allows for more flexible negotiations, no single group can dominate the discussion” (Gov’t Official 3).

A third noted,

“Sometimes, when TTU becomes very active, we see more attention going to other groups too, it creates some competition” (Gov’t Official 8).

While presented as promoting diversity, such fragmentation serves to weaken collective teacher representation, thereby diminishing TTU’s capacity to mobilize and advocate effectively on behalf of its members. These findings are consistent with existing literature. Kuja (2022) reported in Kenya that external political involvement during union elections contributed to declining member trust and institutional instability. Likewise, Aslam et al. (2019) showed that politically influenced leadership in Indian unions often led to organizational inefficiency and deviation from core objectives. These patterns affirm that political interference is not an isolated or accidental occurrence it is structurally embedded in how states engage with independent unions in many African and Asian contexts.

In the lens of Resource Dependence Theory, these forms of political interference highlight the vulnerability of TTU to external pressures due to its reliance on political actors for legitimacy, legal recognition, and operational space. Political elites, aware of this dependency, use it as leverage to influence leadership decisions and union behavior. The union’s limited control over critical resources renders it susceptible to manipulation and co-optation.

Also, the findings also signal the need for Transformational Leadership within TTU. Leaders who are visionary, inspirational, and member-focused can potentially navigate these pressures by building internal solidarity, increasing transparency in leadership selection, and promoting participatory decision-making. A transformational approach could strengthen

TTU's internal resilience and help it maintain focus on its mission even amid political interference.

The findings indicate that political interference within TTU manifests through manipulation of leadership selection, intrusion into internal operations, and fragmentation of the union's unity. Leadership selection processes appear to prioritize political affiliation over professional merit, weakening democratic accountability and reducing members' confidence in their leaders. This aligns with Kuja (2022), who observed that leadership elections within the Kenya National Union of Teachers (KNUT) were manipulated to install politically loyal leaders, resulting in weakened cohesion and redirection of the union's mission toward political survival. Similar patterns were noted in Tanzania by Ng'eleshi et al. (2022), who highlighted that politically aligned leaders diminish TTU's bargaining power. Zulu (2021), who found COSATU's alignment with the ANC diluted its worker-focused mission. This deliberate promotion of alternative unions weakens TTU's unity and bargaining strength. This reflects Elias and Iramba's (2022) observation that multiple politically influenced unions in Tanzania foster internal divisions and diminish collective advocacy.

4.2 The impact of political interference on TTU's internal governance, leadership, and Decision-making processes

Political interference disrupted TTU's internal governance systems

The perspectives gathered from teachers, TTU leaders, and government officials highlight a shared recognition that the union's internal operations are subject to political influence, often at the expense of democratic principles, transparency, and effective representation.

From the teachers' perspective, many expressed frustrations with what they described as politically motivated behaviour among TTU leaders. Respondents observed that some leaders show greater loyalty to political actors than to the teachers they are supposed to represent. One teacher remarked,

"You can see a leader avoiding any strong comment about the government even when teachers are suffering. They fear losing their position" (Teacher 12).

Another teacher noted,

"Some TTU officials act like politicians. They spend more time in political meetings than listening to our problems" (Teacher 18).

A third respondent emphasized,

"Even when we try to raise issues, they delay because they have to first check with political bosses" (Teacher 5).

These reflections suggest that TTU leadership decisions are often shaped by external considerations rather than member needs. The resulting passivity and reluctance to confront state actors undercut the union's role as a representative body. As Traianou (2023) explains, when union leaders align too closely with political forces, they risk neglecting their representative duties and lose credibility among their constituencies.

Political interference weakened leadership autonomy

TTU leaders themselves acknowledged the challenges of maintaining autonomy in a politically charged environment. Several admitted that their freedom to act is constrained by expectations from political authorities. While they are formally elected to serve union members, they often face implicit or explicit pressure to conform to government positions. One leader candidly stated,

“We cannot always say what we want. There are things we avoid because we don’t want to appear like we are fighting the government” (Leader 4).

Another commented,

“Some decisions we make are influenced by people outside the union. We are expected to support certain positions” (Leader 8).

A third leader noted,

“I have seen colleagues removed because they questioned certain government policies. That fear is always there” (Leader 2).

These testimonies demonstrate the political constraints shaping TTU’s leadership culture. As Mndeme (2023) argues, such dynamics erode internal governance structures by replacing meritocratic leadership with politically compliant figures. Mbandlwa et al. (2020) also found that political interference causes local leaders to prioritize loyalty over genuine service delivery, a pattern that appears replicated in the TTU context.

Political interference constrained its decision-making processes

Government officials provided further insight into how political oversight is embedded into TTU’s governance structure. While many officials framed this involvement as necessary for national stability, their narratives revealed a system in which union decisions are often preconditioned by political alignment. One official explained,

“We don’t interfere in everything, but some union decisions must align with national interests. That’s expected” (Gov’t Official 1).

Another admitted,

“Union leaders who are cooperative are easier to work with. We know who will not cause problems” (Gov’t Official 6).

A third shared,

“Sometimes we advise TTU leaders before they take public action. It’s better that way” (Gov’t Official 9).

These perspectives point to a politically centralized model of union leadership in which significant decisions are subjected to prior approval or informal coordination with government entities. This undermines the autonomy that trade unions require to function effectively. As Elias and Iramba (2022) observed, when union leadership is co-opted by political interests, professional independence suffers and focus shifts away from member welfare. Similarly, Ally and John (2021) showed that political entanglement weakens unions’ capacity to address member grievances with integrity.

Applying the Resource Dependence Theory, these findings reinforce the idea that TTU’s structural reliance on state recognition, legal frameworks, and political goodwill exposes it to significant external influence. Political actors, recognizing the union’s dependence, were able to exercise informal control over its leadership behaviour, strategic

decisions, and public positions. This dependency limits TTU's ability to operate as an autonomous entity, particularly when political interests diverge from teacher priorities.

At the same time, the findings demonstrate a clear need for Transformational Leadership within the union. Leaders who can inspire trust, articulate a compelling mission, and challenge the status quo are better positioned to navigate political constraints without compromising the union's values. Inspirational motivation and intellectual stimulation, as described in TLT, could help TTU leaders redefine internal governance processes in ways that emphasize independence, transparency, and collective problem-solving. Transformational leadership is especially critical when formal autonomy is threatened, as it offers a way to rebuild internal legitimacy and strengthen member engagement despite external pressures. The Political interference has profoundly affected TTU's internal governance and leadership culture. Teachers perceive leaders as prioritizing political loyalty over service to members, while leaders themselves admit to avoiding strong positions due to political pressure. This aligns with Traianou (2023), who argued that union officials under political influence neglect their representative duties. Together, the evidence reflects a broader African pattern, comparable to Moswela and Kgosidialwa (2019), where political appointees in education undermine professional leadership.

4.3 Impact of Political Interference on TTU's Service Delivery and Strategic Vision **Political interference constrains TTU's autonomy**

One of the most consistent themes across the interviews was the Political interference constrains TTU's autonomy which causes an erosion of trust and disengagement among union members. Teachers expressed a deep sense of disappointment toward the union, citing its growing alignment with political interests and diminishing responsiveness to member concerns. As one teacher reported,

"Nowadays, many teachers don't even attend TTU meetings. They say it's a waste of time because the union doesn't speak for us anymore" (Teacher 2).

Another teacher explained,

"When you ask for help from TTU, they tell you to wait. But if you are connected politically, your issue is solved quickly" (Teacher 8).

These narratives highlight how TTU's perceived proximity to political actors that eroded its legitimacy, resulting in reduced member participation and lower organizational morale. These findings strongly resonate with Mndeme (2023), who argued that when union leaders are politically aligned, they lose credibility and can no longer serve as genuine representatives.

Political interference undermines its credibility

TTU leaders themselves acknowledged that the union has shifted from proactive advocacy to cautious political appeasement. Leaders reported that concerns about political backlash and the risk of losing their positions have led them to soften their stance and avoid confrontational actions. One leader reflected,

"There was a time when TTU would speak loudly on teacher issues. But now, we must be diplomatic or we face problems" (Leader 5).

Another explained,

"Sometimes we want to organize protests or demand better pay, but we are warned not to be confrontational. So, we just write polite letters" (Leader 2).

These statements illustrate a fundamental transformation in TTU's leadership behavior. Rather than boldly advocating for members, leaders often choose to remain silent or engage in appeasing strategies. This shift is incompatible with the principles of Transformational Leadership Theory, which encourages visionary leadership, risk-taking, and member empowerment. As Traianou (2023) observed, union leaders under political pressure tend to adopt passive strategies that diminish their role as agents of change.

Political interference disrupts the fulfillment of its core goals

Government officials also provided insight into how political interference restricts TTU's ability to implement services and fulfill its strategic mission. Several officials acknowledged that TTU programs are subject to political clearance and that initiatives perceived as too critical of government policy are often blocked or delayed. One official stated,

"Sometimes TTU wants to run teacher awareness programs, but they need clearance. If the message looks too political, it won't be approved"
(Gov't Official 1).

Another noted,

"TTU tries to offer training or push for promotions, but these need collaboration with the Ministry. If there is tension, those plans are frozen" (Gov't Official 6).

These examples confirm that TTU's strategic actions are not entirely within its control but depend on the political goodwill of state authorities. This is precisely what Resource Dependence Theory (RDT) describes how organizations like TTU are constrained by their reliance on external actors who control essential resources such as approvals, legal backing, and institutional recognition. These dynamics have also been discussed by Zulu (2021) and Elias and Iramba (2022), who found that politically compromised unions are forced to adapt their operations to political expectations, undermining their independence and mission-driven focus.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusion

The study confirmed about the political interference experienced by TTU through various channels. Notably, political actors influence leadership appointments, often favoring candidates aligned with political agendas rather than those who are democratically elected by members. The study found the presence of political interference which significantly undermines TTU's internal governance and decision-making processes. The study further revealed the political interference undermines TTU's ability to fulfil its core mandate. Leaders often operate under political pressure, resulting in fear of reprisals or removal if they challenge government policies. This environment stifles dissent, weakens transparency, and erodes the union's democratic ethos. TTU leaders face a dilemma between representing teacher interests and preserving political favor, ultimately leading to internal division and reduced member trust. Political pressure limits the union's willingness to organize collective actions or publicly challenge unfavorable policies. Teachers reported a decline in trust and engagement, citing TTU's perceived alignment with government interests over teacher welfare. Moreover, politically driven bureaucracies often delay or block union initiatives, such as training programs or grievance redress mechanisms. Consequently, TTU's service delivery is compromised, and its mission diluted. These findings reinforce scholarly

arguments that politically influenced unions tend to underperform in member representation and service delivery.

5.2 Recommendations

Addressing the Forms and Sources of Political Interference: TTU should strengthen its internal electoral mechanisms by establishing an independent electoral body to oversee leadership selection. This will minimize political favoritism and ensure leaders are chosen based on merit and member consensus. Furthermore, union by-laws should explicitly prohibit external political interference in union matters. Government institutions must respect TTU's autonomy as stipulated under national labor laws and international labor standards.

i. Enhancing Governance, Leadership, and Decision-Making

Union leaders must engage in regular member consultations and town-hall-style forums to enhance accountability and rebuild trust. The introduction of a transparent code of conduct clearly delineating the responsibilities of union officials and their acceptable relations with political actors will help reduce conflicts of interest. Additionally, TTU should conduct leadership training focused on democratic governance, ethical leadership, and member-centered advocacy to resist external pressures.

ii. Improving Service Delivery and Fulfilment of Union Mission

TTU must adopt a clear advocacy strategy that prioritizes teacher welfare, even in politically sensitive contexts. Strengthening inter-union collaborations across the education sector can reduce fragmentation and amplify collective bargaining power. Additionally, TTU should develop alternative channels such as digital platforms and decentralized regional structures for grievance handling and service delivery, reducing the union's reliance on centralized political approvals.

REFERENCES

- Ally, Z. M., & John, J. (2021). The effectiveness of Trade Union in handling teacher's grievances in public sector. <http://dspace.iaa.ac.tz:8080/xmlui/handle/123456789/1839>
- Elias, Tinus&Iramba, Freddie. (2022). Teachers' Perceptions of Multiple Trade Unions in Promoting Professional Development among Teachers. *Journal La Edusci*. 3. 127-135. 10.37899/journallaedusci. v3i4.735. <http://dx.doi.org/10.37899/journallaedusci.v3i4.735>
- Aslam, M., Rawal, S., & Kingdon, G. (2019). The Political Economy of Teachers in South Asia. *Handbook of Education Systems in South Asia*, 1-23
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2021). To saturate or not to saturate? Questioning data saturation as a useful concept for thematic analysis and sample-size rationales. *Qualitative research in sport, exercise and health*, 13(2), 201-216.
- Haile, E. S., & Smit, B. R. I. G. I. T. T. E. (2021). An investigation to political interference in public secondary school management and leadership practice in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 12(13), 27-42.
- Koliev, F. (2022). Promoting international labour standards: The ILO and national labour regulations. *The British Journal of Politics and International Relations*, 24(2), 361-380. <https://doi.org/10.1177/13691481211027513>

- Kuja, T. O. (2022). Influence of Trade Unions Strategies on Teachers' Welfare in Public Secondary Schools in Nairobi City County, Kenya (Doctoral dissertation, University of Nairobi). <http://erepository.uonbi.ac.ke/handle/11295/163199>
- Melissa, D., & Lisa, M. (2019). Semistructured interviewing in primary care research: A balance of relationship and rigour. *Chinese General Practice*, 22(23), 2786.
- Miyamura, S. (2018). Diverse trajectories of industrial restructuring and labour organising in India. In *Class Dynamics of Development* (pp. 177-198). Routledge. <https://www.taylorfrancis.com/chapters/edit/10.4324/9781315187501-9/diverse-trajectories-industrial-restructuring-labour-organising-india-satoshi-miyamura>
- Moswela, B., & Kgosidialwa, K. (2019). Leadership and school success: Barriers to leadership in Botswana primary and secondary schools. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 47(3), 443-456.
- Mbandlwa, Z., Dorasamy, N., & Fagbadebo, O. M. (2020). Leadership challenges in the South African local government system. *Journal of Critical reviews*.
- Mndeme, O. T. (2023). Decline of Trade Union Collective Action in the Epoch of Neo-Liberal Globalisation: The Experience of Tanzania Teachers' Union. *Tanzania Journal of Sociology*, 8(2), 27-58. <https://www.academia.edu/download/112472744/98.pdf>
- Ng'eleshi, C., Abdi, B., & Chidyau, A. J. (2022). "Extensiveness of Collective Bargaining in Fostering Teachers' Welfare in Public Primary Schools in Moshi Municipality, Tanzania." *British Journal of Education*, 10(12), 32-46.
- Odhiambo, D. O. (2019). How the politics of teacher unions affect teacher benefits.
- Oghlanian, P. H., Qureshi, I. A., & Rasool, R. G. (2023). Trade Unions and Economic Stability: A Case Study of USA Based Auto Industry. *International Multidisciplinary Journal of Science, Technology & Business*, 2(04), 47-52.
- Orelowitz, Menachem Mendel. (2022). Analysing the state of trade union membership in South Africa [Master's dissertation, University of the Witwatersrand, Johannesburg]. WireDSpace. <https://hdl.handle.net/10539/38855>
- Palinkas, L. A., Horwitz, S. M., Green, C. A., Wisdom, J. P., Duan, N., & Hoagwood, K. (2015). Purposeful sampling for qualitative data collection and analysis in mixed method implementation research. *Administration and policy in mental health and mental health services research*, 42, 533-544.
- Reddy, N. (2024). Revisiting Radical Reform? Strategic Dilemma's Facing the South African Labor Movement
- Salmona, M., & Kaczynski, D. (2024). Qualitative data analysis strategies. In *How to conduct qualitative research in finance* (pp. 80-96). Edward Elgar Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.4337/9781803927008.00012>
- Tanzania Teachers Union (2024). About Us. Retrieved from <https://ttu.or.tz>
- Traianou, A. (2023). Evaluation and its politics: trade unions and education reform in Greece. *Education Inquiry*, 1-20.
- Visser, J. (2019). Trade unions in the balance. ILO ACTRAV working paper, 9-11. https://etufegypt.com/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/wcms_722482.pdf
- Wehner, L. E., & Thies, C. G. (2021). Leader influence in role selection choices: Fulfilling role theory's potential for foreign policy analysis. *International Studies Review*, 23(4), 1424-1441. <https://doi.org/10.1093/isr/viab014>
- Yin, R. K. (2018). *Case study research and applications: Design and methods* (6th ed.). SAGE Publications
- Zulu, O. P. (2021). The role of trade unions in advancing a just transition 'in South Africa: a case of COSATU's perspective and approach to climate change.